

Decomposing data systems for better performance

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About Voltron Data

Mission: Leading designer and builder of composable and accelerated data systems

Founded: 2021, formally launched in 2022

Funding: \$110 million in seed and Series A

Advancing Open Source Standards:

- Being the core maintainers for Arrow, Ibis, Substrait, Parquet, and more
- Working with world's biggest organizations like HPE, Meta and Snowflake, on data analytics acceleration with a focus on open source integration and development

Products:

- Enterprise support for open source projects
- Theseus Data Processing Engine

Target Customers: Customers that have very large, complex columnar data sets and workflows (e.g., AI/ML, Geospatial systems used in threat/anomaly detection, predictive maintenance, genomics, and recommenders)

Multi-institutional team earns Gordon Bell Special Prize finalist nomination for rapid COVID-19 molecular docking simulations

November 18, 2020

Topic: Supercomputing

A docking example emphasizing how pockets in the SARS-CoV-2 main protease can be occupied by small molecules in different configurations, with the black molecule representing an experimentally determined position and yellow representing a simulated position. Credit: Joshua Vermaas/ORNL, U.S. Dept. of Energy

One of the biggest challenges of drug discovery lies in the fact that scientists must search through an almost infinite space of chemical compounds to find one that might be capable of interfering with the infectious disease process. When the SARS-CoV-2 virus that causes COVID-19 began sweeping the globe, scientists knew that finding treatments would be no easy feat. The novel coronavirus was uncharted territory. Any protein–small molecule interaction might be the key to thwarting it.

RESEARCHERS

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Multi-institutional team earns Gordon Bell Special Prize finalist nomination for rapid COVID-19 molecular docking simulations

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To analyze the massive amount of data – 1.3 terabytes per large-scale calculation – the team implemented a “virtual laboratory” on Summit to sort, manipulate, and join data pieces together. By **employing the BlazingSQL platform, NVIDIA RAPIDS, and the Dask ecosystem** to query data, the team reduced the processing of their results by orders of magnitude, achieving a 52-fold speedup for the full pipeline.

A docking example emphasizing how pockets in the SARS-CoV-2 main protease can be occupied by small molecules in different configurations, with the black molecule representing an experimentally determined position and yellow representing a simulated position. Credit: Joshua Vermaas/ORNL, U.S. Dept. of Energy

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\$110M Seed and Series A

BlackRock **FACTORY** **iqt** IN-Q-TEL™
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Data systems are about to hit a wall

- Data is preprocessed to feed AI systems. That preprocessing happens on Spark and similar CPU-based systems.
- Scaling out Spark to **feed GPU-powered AI systems** is becoming exponentially more expensive every year.
 - The performance divergence between GPUs and CPUs is only getting worse.
 - Today: 1,000s of Spark nodes needed per GPU rack.
 - Tomorrow: 10,000s of Spark nodes needed per GPU rack.
- Top tier AI companies are already constrained. They cannot ramp up AI capabilities fast enough because they cannot afford to build out Spark clusters fast enough.³
- **We need accelerated data processing engines (compute, memory, networking, storage).**

1. Source: [Compute Trends Across Three Eras of Machine Learning](#)
2. Source: [TPC-H Results](#)
3. Source: [ML Training Growing Pains at Facebook](#)

For Every 5x performance Gain per AI Server ETL Needs 50x the Compute to Sustain

The Build-Your-Own-Database Movement

Enterprises are building custom data systems, that are:

- A critical business differentiator for their end customers, but
- Incredibly expensive, and
- Need to continuously keep up with new advancements.

Voltron Data is **NOT building a database**; we help companies build Arrow-Native Data Systems better, faster, and stronger.

A Composable Data System

Standards

- 1 Substrait is a standard **query plan representation**
- 2 **ADBC** is a standard **client database API**
- 3 Arrow is a standard **columnar data format**

The needs of data systems are growing

Businesses need to support more complex requirements for their data infrastructure.

Apache Arrow

- Apache Arrow is a platform for *in-memory analytics*. It contains a set of technologies that enable big data systems to *process and move data fast*.
- It specifies a *standardized language-independent columnar memory format* for flat and hierarchical data, organized for efficient analytic operations on modern hardware.
- Arrow was originally built at Cloudera and released in 2016.

What is Arrow?

At its core,
a standardized
in-memory
columnar
format for
structured data

Why Arrow?

**Eliminates data
serialization time
and cost**

**Reduces data
transport time and
cost**

**Simplifies and
unifies third-party
integrations**

What else is Arrow?

What else is Arrow?

A set of **libraries** in 13+ languages that implement the format and provide useful tools

What else is Arrow?

A set of **libraries** in 13+ languages that

C, C++, C#, Go,
Java, JavaScript,
Julia, MATLAB,
Python, R, Ruby,
Rust, Swift

What else is Arrow?

A set of **interfaces** for exchanging Arrow-formatted data

What else is Arrow?

A set of **interfaces** for

C data interface, C stream interface, IPC file format, IPC stream format, Flight RPC, Flight SQL, ADBC

What else is Arrow?

An ecosystem of **integrations** of Arrow into third-party products, projects, tools, frameworks, ...

What else is Arrow?

An ecosystem of
integrations

Athena, BigQuery,
ClickHouse, Dask, Dremio,
DuckDB, Hugging Face,
InfluxDB, pandas, Parquet,
Polars, Ray, Snowflake,
Streamlit, Spark, Velox, ...

Arrow HTTP Data Transport

Voltron Data is developing a specification for how to transport Arrow-formatted data over HTTP APIs.

What about Arrow Flight?

- [Arrow Flight](#) is an RPC framework.
- It is based on gRPC over HTTP/2.
- It cannot be directly used in REST or other HTTP/1.1-based APIs.

Early decisions made

- This specification will be separate from the Flight subproject and will not use the “Flight” name.
- Data will be serialized as an [Arrow IPC stream](#) of Arrow record batches, with IANA media type `application/vnd.apache.arrow.stream`.

Items of work

Open source

- Run experiments to determine best approaches.
- Draft an initial version of the specification.
- Iterate to extend and improve the specification.
- Obtain consensus from the Arrow maintainers.
- Publish the specification on the Arrow website.
- Encourage the broader Arrow community to adopt this specification.

Snowflake-specific

- Incorporate Snowflake functional and performance requirements.
- Provide guidance and consultation on implementation in the Snowflake REST APIs.

Progress to date

Complete

- Started [discussion](#) with Arrow developers.
- Reached consensus on early decisions.
- Developed first [client and server prototypes](#).
- Optimized performance of prototypes.

Up next

- Determine Snowflake requirements.
- Develop additional prototypes.
- Investigate outstanding questions.
- Conduct more performance tests.

Row

ID	X	Y	Z	Temp
1	2.5	7.4	1.2	20
2	7.6	3.9	2.2	21
3	5.6	3.4	9.1	19
4	8.0	6.4	5.1	20

Column

ID	X
1	2.5
2	7.6
3	5.6
4	8.0

ID	Y
1	7.4
2	3.9
3	3.4
4	6.4

ID	Z
1	1.2
2	2.2
3	9.1
4	5.1

ID	Temp
1	20
2	21
3	19
4	20

Row vs Column in Storage

ID	X	Y	Z	Temp
1	2.5	7.4	1.2	20
2	7.6	3.9	2.2	21
3	5.6	3.4	9.1	19
4	8.0	6.4	5.1	20

1	2.5	7.4	1.2	20	2	7.6	3.9	2.2	21	3	5.6	3.4	9.1	19	4	8.0	6.4	5.1	20
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Row vs Column in Storage

ID	X	Y	Z	Temp
1	2.5	7.4	1.2	20
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3	5.6	3.4	9.1	19
4	8.0	6.4	5.1	20

X	2.5	7.6	5.6	8.0
----------	-----	-----	-----	-----

Y	7.4	3.9	3.4	6.4
----------	-----	-----	-----	-----

Z	1.2	2.2	9.1	5.1
----------	-----	-----	-----	-----

Temp	20	21	19	20
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- + Compression
- + Less data transfer
- + Lower system burden

Now that we're columnar...

Connect - Data Access with Arrow

Current State: Data Silos Lock You Down

Many companies have many data silos each with different access patterns. Unifying data access can be challenging.

The New Way Forward: Take Flight with Arrow

By leveraging Arrow Flight, companies can provide a simple access protocol (Arrow Flight) and consistent data format (Arrow). No migrations needed.

Compute Mesh

An underlying compute mesh unifying hardware, languages, and frameworks through Theseus.

- 1 Solves problems too big for Spark
- 2 Built for accelerators
- 3 A composable engine that seamlessly plugs in and continues to evolve

Here's what this looks like in HPC

